

Theoretical Analysis of The Thermodynamic Behaviour of Fe-Ni-Pd Melts at 1873K

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Abstract

The concentration dependent thermodynamic behaviour of Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K has been analysed in terms of the excess free energy of mixing, free energy of mixing, activity coefficient and activity of first element i.e. Fe on applying MIVM known as molecular interaction volume model. The computations of the mentioned thermodynamic functions require the input parameters which are ascertained from the parameters needed for the concerned binary system at 1873 K. The theoretical values for the excess free energy of mixing and activity computed from the analytical expressions deduced in the framework of MIVM, are in well agreement with the corresponding experimental results. The concentration dependence of the excess free energy of mixing, free energy of mixing, activity coefficient and activity of first element i.e. Fe for Fe-Ni-Pd system at 1873 K for three cross-sections namely $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$ indicate that Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K is more stable for cross-section 1:1 followed by 1:2 and 1:3 respectively.

Keywords: MIVM model; excess free energy of mixing; activity coefficient; activity; free energy of mixing; Fe-Ni-Pd melts

1. Introduction

Fe-Ni-Pd liquid alloy is composed of three constituents like Fe, Ni and Pd. Obviously, three binaries namely Fe-Ni, Fe-Pd and Ni-Pd are associated with Fe-Ni-Pd alloys. The Fe-Ni-Pd system has wide range of applications in material science as well as geoscience as high temperature alloys component of earth's core, magnetic material etc. Therefore, Fe-Ni-Pd system become suitable for welding, casting, high temperature applications etc. Earlier, the morphological, crystallographical and martensitic characteristics of Fe-Ni-Pd system has been investigated experimentally [1]. The characteristics of Fe-Ni-Pd system relies upon the composition of phase relationship.

Therefore, the experimental studies of the phase diagram have been performed for Fe-Ni-Pd, and Fe-Ni-Pd- based multicomponent alloys namely Fe-Ni-Pd-S [2,3,4,5]. However, there is scarcity of theoretical and experimental data of the thermodynamics of Fe-Ni-Pd melts in the literature. Thus, Fe-Ni-Pd liquid alloy becomes a suitable candidate for the theoretical exploration.

For the understanding of the thermodynamic behaviour of Fe-Ni-Pd alloys, it is necessary to have the knowledge of the mixing properties of the concerned binary alloys like Fe-Ni, Fe-Pd and Ni-Pd. The concentration dependent thermodynamic properties refer to the segregating nature of Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K and Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K as well as ordering nature of Fe-Ni melts at 1873 K [6]. It is interesting to mention that Fe-Pd system possess chemical complexes like FePd, FePd₃, Fe₂Pd and FePd₂ [6, 7]. The interesting thermodynamic behaviour and potential applications i.e. in aerospace, telecommunications, electronics, gas turbine engines, magnetostrictive technologies, spintronic, biomedical applications, electrochemistry, as catalyst etc. of Fe-Ni melts, Fe-Pd melts and Ni-Pd melts have drawn the attentiveness of several researchers [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. Therefore, the ternary system i.e. Fe-Ni-Pd melt is an interesting material which requires a theoretical exploration.

In present research work, MIVM approach [15] is employed for the analysis of the thermodynamic properties namely excess free energy of mixing, G_M^E , free energy of mixing, G_M , activity coefficient and activity of Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K. Earlier, the thermodynamics of several binary liquid alloys such as Zn-Bi, Au-Ni, Au-Cu, Au-Pd, Ti-Al, Zn-Cd etc [17,18,19,20] and several ternary liquid alloys namely In-Bi-Sn, Al-Sn-Zn, Sn-Ag-Cu etc[21,22,23,24] by MIVM model.

2. Formalism

The fluid based model, MIVM (i.e. molecular interaction volume model) has been described by Tao, 2000 [15] and obtained from statistical thermodynamics, fluid-phase equilibria and the fundamental concept of the non-random exchange of liquid molecules. The molecular excess free energy of mixing of the ternary molten alloys (1-2-3) is expressed as [15]

$$\frac{G_M^E}{RT} = x_1 \left(\frac{V_{m1}}{x_1 V_{m1} + x_2 V_{m2} A_{21} + x_3 V_{m3} A_{31}} \right) + x_2 \ln \left(\frac{V_{m2}}{x_2 V_{m2} + x_1 V_{m1} A_{12} + x_3 V_{m3} A_{32}} \right) + x_3 \ln \left(\frac{V_{m3}}{x_3 V_{m3} + x_1 V_{m1} A_{13} + x_2 V_{m2} A_{23}} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left[\begin{array}{l} Z_1 x_1 \left(\frac{x_2 A_{21} \ln A_{21} + x_3 A_{31} \ln A_{31}}{x_1 + x_2 A_{21} + x_3 A_{31}} \right) \\ + Z_2 x_2 \left(\frac{x_1 A_{12} \ln A_{12} + x_3 A_{32} \ln A_{32}}{x_1 A_{12} + x_2 + x_3 A_{32}} \right) \\ + Z_3 x_3 \left(\frac{x_1 A_{13} \ln A_{13} + x_2 A_{23} \ln A_{23}}{x_1 A_{13} + x_2 A_{23} + x_3} \right) \end{array} \right] \quad (1)$$

where, Z_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) stands for the first coordination numbers for the constituent molecules 1,2 and 3 respectively, x_i ($i = 1,2,3$) represents the concentration (or mole fraction) of the constituents 1,2 and 3 respectively A_{12} , A_{21} ; A_{23} , A_{32} ; and A_{31} , A_{13} denote the pair-potential energy interaction parameters between the constituent

elements 1-2, 2-3 and 1-3 for the concerned binary systems (1-2), (2-3) and (1-3) respectively, V_{m1} , V_{m2} and V_{m3} molar volume of elements 1, 2 and 3 respectively. Since, the ternary system (1-2-3) is composed of three binary systems (1-2), (2-3) and (1-3). Therefore, the potential energy interaction parameters are determined for each binary system.

Let us consider a binary system ($i-j$) for which the expression molar excess free energy of mixing may be represented by [15]

$$\frac{G_M^E}{RT} = x_i \ln \left(\frac{V_{mi}}{x_i V_{mi} + x_j V_{mj} A_{ji}} \right) + x_j \ln \left(\frac{V_{mj}}{x_j V_{mj} + x_i V_{mi} A_{ij}} \right) - \frac{x_i x_j}{2} \left(\frac{Z_i A_{ji} \ln A_{ji}}{x_i + x_j A_{ji}} + \frac{Z_j A_{ij} \ln A_{ij}}{x_j + x_i A_{ij}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where, x_i and x_j are the compositions (or mole fractions) of i and j components respectively, Z_i and Z_j stands for the first coordination numbers for the constituent molecules i and j respectively. A_{ij} and A_{ji} denote the pair-potential energy interaction parameters and V_{mi} and V_{mj} are the molar volumes of elements i and j respectively.

Now, A_{ij} and A_{ji} may be expressed as [15]

$$A_{ji} = \exp \left[\frac{\varepsilon_{ji} - \varepsilon_{ii}}{kT} \right] \text{ and } A_{ij} = \exp \left[\frac{\varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{jj}}{kT} \right] \quad (3)$$

with, ε_{ii} , ε_{jj} and ε_{ji} refer to pair potential energies for $i-i$, $j-j$ and $i-j$ respectively, so that $\varepsilon_{ji} = \varepsilon_{ij}$, k and T represent Boltzmann constant and absolute temperature of the binary liquid alloy respectively.

Again, the value of co-ordination number of an element of the binary system can be determined from the relation given below

$$Z_i = \frac{4\sqrt{2}\pi}{3} \left(\frac{r_{mi}^3 - r_{oi}^3}{r_{mi} - r_{oi}} \right) \rho_i r_{mi} \exp \left(\frac{\Delta H_{mi}(T_{mi} - T)}{Z_c R T T_{mi}} \right) \quad (4)$$

with ΔH_{mi} and T_{mi} are enthalpy at melting temperature and melting temperature respectively; Z_c is taken to be 12 for closed packed structure; $\rho_i = N_i V_i = \frac{0.6022}{V_{mi}}$ = molecular number density; r_{mi} and r_{oi} = initial and first peak

values of radial distribution function of the molten metal i near to melting temperature respectively, and R is the molar gas constant. The radial distances are expressed as

$$r_{oi} = 0.918 d_{cov i} \text{ and } r_{mi} = \sigma_i \quad (5)$$

where, σ_i and $d_{cov i}$ = atomic diameter and atomic covalent diameter respectively.

The activity coefficients of the component μ ($= i, j$) of a binary melt in terms of G_M^E can be expressed as [24]

$$RT \ln \gamma_{\mu} = G_M^E + (1-x_{\mu}) \frac{\partial G_M^E}{\partial x_{\mu}}$$

Therefore,

$$\ln \gamma_{\mu} = \frac{G_M^E}{RT} + \frac{(1-x_{\mu})}{RT} \frac{\partial G_M^E}{\partial x_{\mu}} \quad (6)$$

From equation (6), the activity coefficients for constituents i and j of the binary melt $i-j$ can be represented respectively as

$$\ln \gamma_i = \frac{G_M^E}{RT} + \frac{x_j}{RT} \frac{\partial G_M^E}{\partial x_i} \quad (7)$$

$$\ln \gamma_j = \frac{G_M^E}{RT} + \frac{x_i}{RT} \frac{\partial G_M^E}{\partial x_j} \quad (8)$$

where, $x_j = (1-x_i)$ and $x_i = (1-x_j)$

Employing equation (2) in (7) and (8), we can obtain respectively

$$\ln \gamma_i = \ln \left(\frac{V_{mi}}{x_i V_{mi} + x_j V_{mj} A_{ji}} \right) + x_j \left(\frac{V_{mj} A_{ji}}{x_i V_{mi} + x_j V_{mj} A_{ji}} - \frac{V_{mi} A_{ji}}{x_j V_{mj} + x_i V_{mi} A_{ij}} \right) - \frac{x_j^2}{2} \left(\frac{Z_i A_{ji}^2 \ln A_{ji}}{(x_i + x_j A_{ji})^2} + \frac{Z_j A_{ij} \ln A_{ji}}{(x_j + x_i A_{ij})^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\ln \gamma_j = \ln \left(\frac{V_{mj}}{x_j V_{mj} + x_i V_{mi} A_{ij}} \right) - x_i \left(\frac{V_{mj} A_{ji}}{x_i V_{mi} + x_j V_{mj} A_{ji}} - \frac{V_{mi} A_{ij}}{x_j V_{mj} + x_i V_{mi} A_{ij}} \right) - \frac{x_i^2}{2} \left(\frac{Z_j A_{ij}^2 \ln A_{ij}}{(x_j + x_i A_{ij})^2} + \frac{Z_i A_{ji} \ln A_{ij}}{(x_i + x_j A_{ji})^2} \right) \quad (10)$$

The equations (9) and (10) are the analytical expressions from which γ_i and γ_j of the binary melt $i-j$ can be computed.

From definition, the activity coefficient and activity of the component μ of a binary melt are related as

$$a_{\mu} = \gamma_{\mu} x_{\mu} \quad (\text{where, } \mu = i, j)$$

(11)

From equation (11), the activities of the components i and j of the binary melt $i-j$ can be expressed as

$$a_i = \gamma_i x_i$$

(12)

$$a_j = \gamma_j x_j$$

(13)

The equations (12) and (13) can be utilized to determine the activities a_i and a_j respectively of the binary melt $i-j$.

The expressions for activity coefficients of the components of the alloy in infinite dilute solution range i.e. x_i or $x_i \rightarrow 0$, are, respectively, given by

$$\ln \gamma_i^\infty = 1 - \ln \left(\frac{V_{mj} A_{ji}}{V_{mi}} \right) - \frac{V_{mi} A_{ji}}{V_{mj}} - \frac{1}{2} (Z_i \ln A_{ji} + Z_j A_{ij} \ln A_{ij}) \quad (14)$$

and

$$\ln \gamma_j^\infty = 1 - \ln \left(\frac{V_{mi} A_{ij}}{V_{mj}} \right) - \frac{V_{mj} A_{ji}}{V_{mi}} - \frac{1}{2} (Z_j \ln A_{ij} + Z_i A_{ji} \ln A_{ji}) \quad (15)$$

The pair-potential energy interaction parameters, A_{ij} and A_{ji} can be determined by solving equation (14) and (15) on applying Newton-Rapson method.

Now, for a ternary melt (1-2-3), the activity coefficient of the component i is expressed as [15]

$$RT \ln \gamma_i = G_M^E + x_2 \left(\frac{\partial G_M^E}{\partial x_1} \right) - x_3 \left(\frac{\partial G_M^E}{\partial x_3} \right) \quad (16)$$

Using equation (1) in (16), we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \gamma_i = 1 + \ln & \left(\frac{V_{m1}}{x_1 V_{m1} + x_2 V_{m2} A_{21} + x_3 V_{m3} A_{31}} \right) - \frac{x_1 V_{m1}}{x_1 V_{m1} + x_2 V_{m2} A_{21} + x_3 V_{m3} A_{31}} \\ & - \frac{x_2 V_{m1} A_{12}}{x_1 V_{m1} A_{12} + x_2 V_{m2} + x_3 V_{m3} A_{32}} - \frac{x_3 V_{m1} A_{13}}{x_1 V_{m1} A_{13} + x_2 V_{m2} A_{23} + x_3 V_{m3}} \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{Z_1 (x_2 A_{21} + x_3 A_{31}) (x_2 A_{21} \ln A_{21} + x_3 A_{31} \ln A_{31})}{(x_1 + x_2 A_{21} + x_3 A_{31})^2} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{Z_2 x_2 A_{21} [(x_2 + x_3 A_{32}) \ln A_{12} - x_3 A_{32} \ln A_{32}]}{(x_1 A_{12} + x_2 + x_3 A_{32})^2} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{Z_3 x_3 A_{13} [(x_2 A_{23} + x_3) \ln A_{13} - x_2 A_{23} \ln A_{23}]}{(x_1 A_{13} + x_2 A_{23} + x_3)^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

which is the analytical expression for the activity coefficient of the component i of a ternary system (1-2-3).

Now, the activity coefficient and activity of the component 1 may be related as

$$a_1 = \gamma_1 x_1 \quad (18)$$

The equation (17) and (18) are utilized to determine the theoretical values of the activity of component i of a ternary system (1-2-3).

Now, the free energy of mixing, G_M for a ternary system may be represented as

$$\frac{G_M}{RT} = \frac{G_M^E}{RT} + \frac{G_M^{id}}{RT} \quad (19)$$

Again, for a ternary system, the ideal free energy of mixing, G_M^{id} at a given temperature T may be represented by

$$G_M^{id} = RT [x_1 \ln x_1 + x_2 \ln x_2 + x_3 \ln x_3] \quad (20)$$

Using equation (1) and (20), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{G_M}{RT} = & x_1 \left(\frac{V_{m1}}{x_1 V_{m1} + x_2 V_{m2} A_{21} + x_3 V_{m3} A_{31}} \right) + x_2 \ln \left(\frac{V_{m2}}{x_2 V_{m2} + x_1 V_{m1} A_{12} + x_3 V_{m3} A_{32}} \right) \\ & + x_3 \ln \left(\frac{V_{m3}}{x_3 V_{m3} + x_1 V_{m1} A_{13} + x_2 V_{m2} A_{23}} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left[\begin{aligned} & Z_1 x_1 \left(\frac{x_2 A_{21} \ln A_{21} + x_3 A_{31} \ln A_{31}}{x_1 + x_2 A_{21} + x_3 A_{31}} \right) \\ & + Z_2 x_2 \left(\frac{x_1 A_{12} \ln A_{12} + x_3 A_{32} \ln A_{32}}{x_1 A_{12} + x_2 + x_3 A_{32}} \right) \\ & + Z_3 x_3 \left(\frac{x_1 A_{13} \ln A_{13} + x_2 A_{23} \ln A_{23}}{x_1 A_{13} + x_2 A_{23} + x_3} \right) \end{aligned} \right] \\ & + [x_1 \ln x_1 + x_2 \ln x_2 + x_3 \ln x_3] \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

which is the required analytical expression for G_M of a ternary liquid alloys.

3. Result and Discussion

The analytical expressions (1), (21), (17) and (18) are employed to compute G_M^E / RT , G_M / RT , γ_i and a_i respectively of Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K. For calculations, the input parameters are required which are evaluated from the concerned binary system i.e. Fe-Ni melts at 1873 K, Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K and Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K. The necessary parameters of pure Fe, Ni and Pd are presented in **Table 1** [25]. For a binary system i-j the coordination number Z_i and Z_j of the constituents are determined from equation (4) which are presented in **Table**

2. The values of A_{ji} and A_{ij} are determined on solving equations (14) and (15) by Newton-Rapson method by using the experimental values of infinite dilute activity coefficients i.e. γ_i^∞ and γ_j^∞ [6]. The values of A_{ji} and A_{ij} slightly changed [15] in order to achieve a good agreement between the theory and experiment [6] for the excess free energy of mixing, G_M^E / RT for the concerned binary alloys. The best fit values A_{ji} and A_{ij} at required temperature are depicted in **Table 2**.

Table 1. Input parameters for the pure metals [25]

Metal, i	ΔH_{mi} (KJ/mol)	σ_i ($\times 10^{-8}$ cm)	r_{oi} ($\times 10^{-8}$ cm)	v_{mi} (cm^3/mol)
Fe	13.77	2.56	1.98	$7.94[1+1.3 \times 10^{-4}(T-1808)]$
Ni	17.15	2.50	1.88	$7.43[1+1.3 \times 10^{-4}(T-1728)]$
Pd	16.7	2.75	2.56	$10.14[1+1.17 \times 10^{-4}(T-1828)]$

Table 2: Input Parameters for Binary Systems

$i-j$	T (K)	V_{mi}	V_{mj}	A_{ij}	A_{ji}	Z_i	Z_j	γ_i^∞	γ_j^∞
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		(cm ³ /mole)	(cm ³ /mole)						
Fe-Ni	1873	8.01	7.59	1.1037	1.0191	10.00	9.74	0.355	0.617
Ni-Pd	1873	7.59	10.19	0.9757	0.9395	9.74	11.53	2.306	2.805
Fe-Pd	1873	8.01	10.19	0.8761	0.9915	10.00	11.53	1.546	1.683

3.1 Results for G_M^E and a_μ ($\mu = i, j$) of Fe-Ni, Fe-Pd and Ni-Pd at 1873 K

The equation (2) is used to ascertain the values of G_M^E / RT for Fe-Ni, Fe-Pd and Ni-Pd at 1873 K as a function of concentration, x_p ($p = \text{Fe, Fe and Ni}$). The theoretical results and correlated experimental results [6] presented in Fig. 1, exhibit well harmony in the complete range of composition, $x = 0.1$ to 0.9.

For Fe-Ni system at 1873 K, $\frac{G_M^E}{RT}$ vs x_{Fe} isotherm denotes the negative values of $\frac{G_M^E}{RT}$ in the complete composition range of Fe i.e. $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ to 0.9 with minima at $x_{Fe} = 0.4$ i.e. - 0.1853 (Theory) and -0.1777 (Experiment). Thus, the asymmetry in $\frac{G_M^E}{RT}$ as well as ordering nature [26] of Fe-Ni melts at 1873 K are well explained theoretically. It is required to point out that the theoretical results for $\frac{G_M^E}{RT}$ exhibit the marked departures from the experimental results i. e in the regions $0.2 \leq x_{Fe} \leq 0.4$ and $0.6 \leq x_{Fe} \leq 0.8$.

For Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K, in whole composition region, $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ to 0.9, $\frac{G_M^E}{RT}$ exhibits positive value at each concentration with maximum values at $x_{Fe} = 0.5$ i.e. 0.2119 (Theory) and 0.2102 (Experiment). Thus, MIVM successfully represents the symmetry in $\frac{G_M^E}{RT}$ and segregating character [26] of Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K.

For Ni-Pd liquid at 1873 K, $\frac{G_M^E}{RT}$ are positive in the complete composition range of Ni i.e. $x_{Ni} = 0.1$ to 0.9 with maxima at $x_{Ni} = 0.5$ i.e. 0.1209 (Theory) and 0.1194 (Experiment). Thus, the symmetry in $\frac{G_M^E}{RT}$ as well as segregating nature [26] of Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K are successfully explained by MIVM.

Fig. 1 G_M^E/RT vs x_p ($p = \text{Fe, Fe, Ni}$) for Fe-Ni melts at 1873 K, Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K and Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K

For the computations of activity of both the components of each alloy namely Fe-Ni at 1873 K, Fe-Pd at 1873 K and Ni-Pd at 1873 K from the equation (12) and (13), the theoretical values of activity coefficients of both the components of the concerned binary alloys are required. For this, the equations (9) and (10) are utilized to determine the theoretical values of both the components of the alloys Fe-Ni at 1873 K, Fe-Pd at 1873 K and Ni-Pd at 1873 K. The theoretical results and corresponding experimental results [6] for both the components of the alloys under consideration are depicted in **Fig. 2** with respect to concentration.

For Fe-Ni liquid alloys at 1873 K, the theoretical results for a_{Fe} and a_{Ni} relative to x_{Fe} are compared with the corresponding experimental results [6] in **Fig. 2**. A reasonable agreement is observed between theory and experiment. The negative deviations of a_{Fe} and a_{Ni} from ideal mixing behaviour in the concentration region $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ to 0.9 , advocate the ordering character [26] of Fe-Ni melts at 1873 K. It is pointed out that the activity is a fortunate thermodynamic function which is measured by the experiment [26]. Thus, the harmony between theory and experiment authenticates the evaluated values of A_{ji} and A_{ij} .

Fig. 2 indicates that the theoretical values and correlated experimental values [6] for a_{Fe} and a_{Pd} of Fe-Pd System at 1873 K are in well agreement in the complete composition region, $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ to 0.9 . Again, the positive departures of a_{Fe} and a_{Pd} from Raoult's law confirm the segregation [26] in Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K. The agreement between theory and experiment validates the estimated values of A_{ji} and A_{ij} .

For Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K, an excellent similarity is noticed between theory and experiment [6] in the region, $x_{Ni} = 0.1$ to 0.9 for a_{Ni} and a_{Pd} in **Fig. 2**. Again, the small positive departures of a_{Ni} and a_{Pd} from linear law confirm the feebly segregating nature [26] of Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K. Therefore, the agreement between theory

and experiment provides the authenticity of the evaluated values of A_{ji} and A_{ij} .

Fig. 2 Activity vs x_p ($p = \text{Fe, Fe, Ni}$) for Fe-Ni melts at 1873 K, Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K and Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K

3.2 Results for G_M^E / RT , G_M / RT , γ_{Fe} and a_{Fe} of Fe-Ni-Pd Liquid Alloys at 1873 K

In present study, MIVM model has been employed to investigate the thermodynamic behaviour of Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K in terms of G_M^E / RT , G_M / RT , γ_{Fe} and a_{Fe} as a function of concentration of Fe. For the computations of the above thermodynamic properties of Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K, the required input parameters are presented below (taken from **Table 2**):

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{Fe} = V_{m1} &= 8.01 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mole} & V_{Ni} = V_{m2} &= 12.13 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mole} & V_{Pd} = V_{m3} &= 10.19 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mole} \\
 Z_{Fe} = Z_1 &= 10.00 & Z_{Ni} = Z_2 &= 9.74 & Z_{Pd} = Z_3 &= 11.53 \\
 A_{ij} = A_{12} &= 1.1037 & A_{ji} = A_{21} &= 1.0191 & & \text{(for Fe-Ni system at 1873 K)} \\
 A_{jk} = A_{23} &= 0.9757 & A_{kj} = A_{32} &= 0.9395 & & \text{(for Fe-Pd system at 1873 K)} \\
 A_{ik} = A_{13} &= 0.8760 & A_{ki} = A_{31} &= 0.9915 & & \text{(for Ni-Pd system at 1873 K)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, expression (1) is utilized to determine the theoretical values of G_M^E / RT relative to the concentration of Fe for Fe-Ni-Pd liquid alloys at 1873 K for the cross-sections namely, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$. The theoretical values of G_M^E / RT are tabulated in **Table 3** and displayed in **Fig. 3**. It is evident that for cross-sections, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$, G_M^E / RT display the positive values in the complete region of concentration i.e. $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ to 0.9 for Fe-Ni-Pd at 1873 K. Again, the maximum values of G_M^E / RT are 0.1595 at $x_{Fe} = 0.3$ for cross-section $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:3$ followed by 0.1397 at $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ for cross-section $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:2$ and 0.1009 at $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ for cross-section $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1$ respectively. This indicates that Fe-Pd melt dominates over Fe-Ni melt for the cross-

sections $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:3, 1:2$ and $1:1$ in Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K. It is pointed out that no experimental data for Fe-Ni-Pd melts are available in the literature for comparison.

Table 3: G_M^E / RT for Fe-Ni-Pd Ternary Liquid Alloys at 1873 K

For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	G_M^E / RT
0.1000	0.4500	0.4500	0.1009
0.2000	0.4000	0.4000	0.0801
0.3000	0.3500	0.3500	0.0628
0.4000	0.3000	0.3000	0.0484
0.5000	0.2500	0.2500	0.0365
0.6000	0.2000	0.2000	0.0267
0.7000	0.1500	0.1500	0.0186
0.8000	0.1000	0.1000	0.0117
0.9000	0.0500	0.0500	0.0057
For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:2$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	G_M^E / RT
0.1000	0.3000	0.6000	0.1397
0.2000	0.2667	0.5333	0.1349
0.3000	0.2333	0.4667	0.1287
0.4000	0.2000	0.4000	0.1205
0.5000	0.1667	0.3333	0.1098
0.6000	0.1333	0.2667	0.0961
0.7000	0.1000	0.2000	0.0789
0.8000	0.0667	0.1333	0.0575
0.9000	0.0333	0.0667	0.0314
For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:3$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	G_M^E / RT
0.1000	0.2250	0.6750	0.1553
0.2000	0.2000	0.6000	0.1594
0.3000	0.1750	0.5250	0.1595
0.4000	0.1500	0.4500	0.1551
0.5000	0.1250	0.3750	0.1455
0.6000	0.1000	0.3000	0.1302
0.7000	0.0750	0.2250	0.1087

0.8000	0.0500	0.1500	0.0803
0.9000	0.0250	0.0750	0.0443

Fig. 3 G_M^E/RT vs x_{Fe} for Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K for cross-sections, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2 \text{ \& } 1:3$

Expression (21) is used to ascertain the theoretical values of G_M / RT for Fe-Ni-Pd liquid alloys at 1873 K for three cross-section namely, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$ in terms of the concentration of Fe. The theoretical values of G_M / RT are included in **Table 4** and illustrated in **Fig. 4**. It is clear that G_M / RT is negative at each concentration of Fe for Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K for each cross-section i.e. 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 in the complete region of concentration i.e. $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ to 0.9 . The values of G_M / RT are minimum at $x_{Fe} = 0.4$ i.e. -1.0405 for cross-section 1:1, -0.9345 for cross-section 1:2 and -0.8553 for cross-section 1:3 respectively. Thus, Fe-Ni-Pd system at 1873 K is more stable for cross-section $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1$ followed by $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:2$ and 1:3 respectively.

Table 4: G_M / RT for Fe-Ni-Pd Liquid Alloy at 1873 K

For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1$			
x_{Fe}	G_M^E / RT	G_M^{id} / RT	G_M / RT
0.1000	0.1009	-0.9489	-0.8480
0.2000	0.0801	-1.0549	-0.9748
0.3000	0.0628	-1.0961	-1.0333
0.4000	0.0484	-1.0889	-1.0405
0.5000	0.0365	-1.0397	-1.0032
0.6000	0.0267	-0.9503	-0.9235
0.7000	0.0186	-0.8188	-0.8002

0.8000	0.0117	-0.6390	-0.6273
0.9000	0.0057	-0.3944	-0.3887
For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:2$			
x_{Fe}	G_M^E / RT	G_M^{id} / RT	G_M / RT
0.1000	0.1397	-0.8979	-0.7582
0.2000	0.1349	-1.0096	-0.8747
0.3000	0.1287	-1.0564	-0.9277
0.4000	0.1205	-1.0549	-0.9345
0.5000	0.1098	-1.0114	-0.9016
0.6000	0.0961	-0.9276	-0.8315
0.7000	0.0789	-0.8018	-0.7230
0.8000	0.0575	-0.6277	-0.5702
0.9000	0.0314	-0.3887	-0.3573

For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:3$			
x_{Fe}	G_M^E / RT	G_M^{id} / RT	G_M / RT
0.1000	0.1553	-0.8312	-0.6759
0.2000	0.1594	-0.9503	-0.7908
0.3000	0.1595	-1.0045	-0.8450
0.4000	0.1551	-1.0104	-0.8553
0.5000	0.1455	-0.9743	-0.8288
0.6000	0.1302	-0.8979	-0.7677
0.7000	0.1087	-0.7796	-0.6709
0.8000	0.0803	-0.6129	-0.5326
0.9000	0.0443	-0.3813	-0.3371

Fig. 4 G_M/RT vs x_{Fe} for Fe-Ni-Pd system at 1873 K for cross-sections, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$

Equation (17) is used to determine the concentration dependence of γ_{Fe} for Fe-Ni-Pd liquid alloys at 1873 K for the cross-sections $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$. The theoretical results are reported in Table 5 and displayed in Fig. 5.

Table 5: Activity Coefficient of Fe in Fe-Ni-Pd Liquid Alloys at 1873 K

For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	γ_{Fe}
0.1000	0.4500	0.4500	0.9026
0.2000	0.4000	0.4000	0.9308
0.3000	0.3500	0.3500	0.9533
0.4000	0.3000	0.3000	0.9704
0.5000	0.2500	0.2500	0.9828
0.6000	0.2000	0.2000	0.9912
0.7000	0.1500	0.1500	0.9963
0.8000	0.1000	0.1000	0.9989
0.9000	0.0500	0.0500	1.0645
For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:2$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	γ_{Fe}
0.1000	0.3000	0.6000	1.1320
0.2000	0.2667	0.5333	1.1159
0.3000	0.2333	0.4667	1.0975
0.4000	0.2000	0.4000	1.0781
0.5000	0.1667	0.3333	1.0587
0.6000	0.1333	0.2667	1.0405
0.7000	0.1000	0.2000	1.0244
0.8000	0.0667	0.1333	1.0116
0.9000	0.0333	0.0667	1.0918

For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:3$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	γ_{Fe}
0.1000	0.2250	0.6750	1.2802
0.2000	0.2000	0.6000	1.2311
0.3000	0.1750	0.5250	1.1843
0.4000	0.1500	0.4500	1.1408
0.5000	0.1250	0.3750	1.1017
0.6000	0.1000	0.3000	1.0678
0.7000	0.0750	0.2250	1.0397
0.8000	0.0500	0.1500	1.0185
0.9000	0.0250	0.0750	1.1062

Fig. 5 γ_{Fe} vs x_{Fe} for Fe-Ni-Pd system at 1873 K for cross-sections, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$

The activity, a_{Fe} for Fe-Ni-Cd at 1873 K has been calculated from equation (18) on using the theoretical results of γ_{Fe} for the cross-sections $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$. The theoretical data for a_{Fe} of Fe-Ni-Cd at 1873 K are presented in Table 6 and illustrated in Fig. 6. It exhibits that a_{Fe} are almost equal to the ideal values in concentration range $0.0 \leq a_{Fe} \leq 0.80$ and positive deviation is noticed in the region $0.80 \leq a_{Fe} \leq 1.0$ for cross-section $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1$.

Table 6: Activity of Fe in Fe-Ni-Pd Liquid Alloys at 1873 K

For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	a_{Fe}
0.1000	0.4500	0.4500	0.090
0.2000	0.4000	0.4000	0.186
0.3000	0.3500	0.3500	0.286

0.4000	0.3000	0.3000	0.388
0.5000	0.2500	0.2500	0.491
0.6000	0.2000	0.2000	0.595
0.7000	0.1500	0.1500	0.697
0.8000	0.1000	0.1000	0.799
0.9000	0.0500	0.0500	0.958
For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:2$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	a_{Fe}
0.1000	0.3000	0.6000	0.113
0.2000	0.2667	0.5333	0.223
0.3000	0.2333	0.4667	0.329
0.4000	0.2000	0.4000	0.431
0.5000	0.1667	0.3333	0.529
0.6000	0.1333	0.2667	0.624
0.7000	0.1000	0.2000	0.717
0.8000	0.0667	0.1333	0.809
0.9000	0.0333	0.0667	0.983
For $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:3$			
x_{Fe}	x_{Ni}	x_{Pd}	a_{Fe}
0.1000	0.2250	0.6750	0.128
0.2000	0.2000	0.6000	0.246
0.3000	0.1750	0.5250	0.355
0.4000	0.1500	0.4500	0.456
0.5000	0.1250	0.3750	0.551
0.6000	0.1000	0.3000	0.641
0.7000	0.0750	0.2250	0.728
0.8000	0.0500	0.1500	0.815
0.9000	0.0250	0.0750	0.996

Fig. 6 a_{Fe} vs x_{Fe} for Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K for cross-sections, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$

4. Conclusions

From present theoretical study, it may concluded that

- The theoretical results for G_M^E / RT and activity of both the components of the binary alloys namely Fe-Ni melts at 1873 K, Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K and Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K, exhibit good harmony with the corresponding experimental results.
- The observed symmetries in G_M^E / RT for Fe-Pd at 1873 K and Ni-Pd at 1873 K as well as asymmetry in G_M^E / RT for Fe-Ni at 1873 K are successfully reproduced.
- The sign of G_M^E / RT in the complete concentration region confirms that Fe-Pd at 1873 K and Ni-Pd at 1873 K are segregating in nature whereas Fe-Ni at 1873 K is an ordering system.
- The positive departures from linear law of the activity of both the components i.e. a_{Fe} and a_{Pd} for Fe-Pd system at 1873 K; a_{Ni} and a_{Pd} for Ni-Pd system at 1873 K, indicate that Fe-Pd melts at 1873 K and Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K are segregating alloys while Fe-Ni melt at 1873 K is an ordered alloy because a_{Fe} and a_{Ni} exhibit negative deviations from linear law.
- The concentration dependence of G_M^E / RT for Fe-Ni-Pd system at 1873 K exhibits positive value at each concentration in the region, $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ to 0.9 for each cross-section namely, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1, 1:2$ and $1:3$.
- In the entire composition range, $x_{Fe} = 0.1$ to 0.9 , G_M / RT of Fe-Ni-Pd melts at 1873 K exhibit negative value at each composition for cross-section under consideration. The magnitude of negative values of G_M / RT justifies that Fe-Ni-Pd system at 1873 K is more stable for cross-section, $x_{Ni} : x_{Pd} = 1:1$ followed by $1:2$ and $1:3$ respectively.
- For each cross-section, the activity of Fe for Fe-Ni-Pd system at 1873 K, indicate positive deviation from linear law.

Thus, MIVM model is a reliable and suitable model to explain the thermodynamic behaviour of binary as well as ternary alloys.

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